

«WORK ON INCREASING THE VOCABULARY OF THE STUDENT IN PRIMARY SCHOOL READING LESSONS»

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Annotation: *this article will provide information on how to work on increasing the vocabulary of a student in elementary school reading lessons.*

Keywords: *Dictionary work, dictionary-grammatical exercises, the meaning of words and phrases, dictionary composition of the Uzbek language.*

In the curriculum of primary classes,, the mother tongue, reading is an important factor in enriching the vocabulary of children, developing coherent speech, perfection of literary-aesthetic thinking, the formation of a culture of speech, ensuring speech sensitivity," - the statement says. These tasks are performed through the study of grammatical topics, observation and analysis of 6 texts of exercises, special lexical grammatical exercises.

In the dictionary work, the meaning, pronunciation and spelling of the word are paid attention. The main purpose of working on these is to achieve the students ' use of them in their speech when there is a need, to enable them to understand other people's speech. To do this, the teacher must pay attention to the meaning of each word used in the lessons of mother tongue and reading, and in the educational process: ecstasy, mutual conversation, words used in various activities, determine which of them should be specially treated. Introduce students to unfamiliar words and phrases. It may be the first time that students encounter words and phrases in the textbook. This word does not know the meaning of the reader, even if it is not a newly appeared word, it means that it is considered a new word for the reader. For example, in the textbook " mother tongue " 1-th class, Habib (friend), dar-veil (window sill with transparent paper instead of window), pride (stuttering, proud — humble), Kemal (comprehensively mature, pour out, find Kemal — Khazan bo 'Imam), ruin (desolation left unattended), sibling (friend, brother, relative-seed), safdash (together in the military 7 service, together in the organization), commander (Commander, Army), they face such words as Zeb (decoration, fur, husn), Kule (luxury palace, mansion). The meaning of such words can be explained by solving the meaning by constructing a sentence, creating an understanding through pictures, by interpreting them with words of opposite meaning, looking at them through synonyms and expansion. Such performance generates sensitivity in students towards word

meanings. Lexicology is a section that studies the composition of the dictionary of the Uzbek language. Lexicology studies the characteristic of the words in the dictionary to express meaning in speech, the activity of application, enrichment, the wear and tear of some words, the withdrawal from consumption, the phenomenon of meaning migration, etc. Therefore, lexicology is the linguistic basis of the methodology of working on the dictionary.[3]

A close understanding of the word itself is an explanation with a different expression. The explanation of the word to be explained in this should be short and clear. For example, self-indulgence is the ability to work at will, to perform work as much as he wants; specialist — the owner of a craft; so - a sharp bird with a long Flying Eye; mesh — a vessel made of moles skin; guldon — a vessel made of flowers, etc. The teacher should know and rely on the changes that occur in the development of speech by the student at each stage of Education. In each lesson, the reader should increase the vocabulary, vocabulary.[4] It will be expedient for the teacher to use modern methods when working on a dictionary, increasing vocabulary. These are the following.

1. Explanation is a method of demonstration. Knowledge is given by the teacher on a ready-made basis. The laws of the native language are explained and strengthened. In this lesson, students listen to the knowledge that is being explained and should try to keep it in memory.

2. Problem statement method. The teacher puts a certain problem that the students receive and begins to solve this problem by providing them with independent mental activity.
3. Partial traceability method. This method of education is thus characteristic that the pupil puts a certain learning problem in the process of the lesson, but does not indicate ways to solve it independently. Each schoolboy is searched independently for a solution to the problem, has creative activity. The problem posed by the teacher makes the method partially creative. When teaching words and syllables, it is customary not to read sounds and characters separately, but to pronounce sounds and letters with the correct addition of syllables in the syllable, to read words in accordance with the harmony of sounds in a holistic state, as in oral speech. Proverbs are of great importance in enriching the speech of students. Proverbs are a very convenient material both for reading, and for conversation, and for compiling a story, and for grammatical analysis and writing. They are compact, imperceptible and impressionable; Proverbs cultivate the artistic taste of students, teach them to look with attention to speech, to think correctly, logically, occupy an important place in aesthetic education. In reading books, depending on the topic, Uzbek textbooks give a lot of Proverbs on different topics in the texts of exercises. Readers, reading the proverbs, associate them with the moral problem of the work read, with life circumstances, explain their figurative meaning, the meaning of some words and phrases. As a result, they begin to use proverbs with a role.

Working on vocabulary in primary school mother tongue and reading lessons will serve as a key factor in increasing students ' vocabulary

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